

Supplementary Material 2: Recruitment and Field Documents

- a. Cat management study: recruitment leaflet and example of social media post
- b. Ammunition study: letter of invitation
- c. Cat management study: information for participants
- d. Translocation study: information for participants
- e. Consent form (variation on template used for all studies)

CAT OWNERS WANTED

We are looking for cat owners of all kinds to take part in our research.

We're interested in your views on a range of issues relating to keeping cats, including indoor/outdoor access, environmental risks to cat health and welfare, and hunting behaviour.

Taking part will involve a meeting with a researcher, at your convenience.

For more information and to sign up, visit:

www.wildlifescience.uk/cat-owners

Or contact Dr Sarah Crowley:

07384 242793

s.crowley@exeter.ac.uk

Figure S2a(i): Printed leaflet distributed in pet shops and veterinary practices

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Figure S2a(ii): Attachment for social media recruitment posts, primarily shared on Facebook and email distribution lists.

S2b: Ammunition study: letter of invitation

European Regional
Development Fund
Investing in your Future

convergence
for economic
transformation

ENVIRONMENT AND
SUSTAINABILITY INSTITUTE

Cornwall Campus
Penryn
Cornwall
UK TR10 9EZ

Dear Sir or Madam

Understanding perspectives of the shooting community in the UK on lead shot and the non-toxic alternatives

Letter of Invitation

I am a researcher from the University of Exeter and the Wildfowl & Wetlands Trust, and I am writing to invite you to take part in a research project about lead shot and the non-toxic alternatives.

In recent years, there has been much debate about the risks of lead shot for wildlife and people and the suitability of the non-toxic alternatives. The shooting community play an important role in the management and conservation of the British countryside and also in providing food through shot game. For this reason, we are interested in your thoughts and experiences in relation to these issues. We hope that this study provides an opportunity for the shooting community to fully express its views on this subject.

Taking part involves an informal meeting (1.5 hrs long) with one of the research team at a time and location of your convenience, during which you will be asked to rank a number of opinion statements about the topic according to how strongly you agree or disagree with each one. You will also have the opportunity to expand upon your answers in a short interview afterwards. Participation in this study is entirely voluntary and participants may withdraw at any time. Only the research team will have access to the data we collect. I hope to publish the research and include this as a chapter in my PhD thesis. Participants' identities and associated organisations will be protected and remain anonymous.

If you are interested in participating, or have any questions about the project, please contact me (my contact details are at the bottom of this page). It would also be helpful if you could inform me of your location and some initial information about your involvement with shooting interests. E.g - if you are a shooter, what is your main quarry species? How do you mainly access your shooting - through commercial days, a syndicate/club, through local contacts or any other means (please describe)?

Please also get in touch if you have any questions about this research. A contact email address for my primary research supervisor is also provided below.

Thank you for taking the time to read this invitation, and I look forward to hearing from you.

Yours Sincerely,

Julia Newth (PhD Researcher)

[Redacted contact information]

Primary Supervisor:

Professor Robbie McDonald

[Redacted contact information]

S2c: Cat management study: information for participants

Environment and Sustainability Institute
University of Exeter

Keeping Cats in the UK: Cat Owners' Views Information for Participants

Cats are one of the UK's most popular pets. They are kept by millions of people for companionship and, sometimes, for pest-control purposes. At the University of Exeter's Environment and Sustainability institute, we are working with cat owners to better understand relationships between cats, their owners, and the wider environment.

In this study, we are asking a diverse group of cat owners about their views on a range of issues relating to keeping cats, including indoor/outdoor access, environmental risks to cat health and welfare, and hunting behaviour. We are particularly interested in your views on cat roaming and hunting, but you can take part regardless of whether or not your cat is a hunter or spends time outdoors.

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary. Taking part involves a meeting (~1.5 hours) with one of our research team at a mutually agreed time and location (depending on your location and preference, this may be at your home or an agreed meeting point such as a café or pub). We will ask you to look at some written statements about cats, and rank them according to how much you agree or disagree with each one. We will talk you through the whole process, which most people find interesting and straightforward.

We will then have a short follow-up conversation. With your permission, this will be audio recorded, but recordings will not be shared with anyone outside the research team. You can also ask for the audio recording to be switched off at any time. We may use select quotes from our conversations in future research or publications; these will be anonymised and your identity protected.

Thank you for taking the time to read this invitation, and I look forward to hearing from you. Please get in touch if you have any questions.

Yours faithfully

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sarah Crowley'.

Dr Sarah Crowley
Associate Research Fellow

S2d: Translocation study: information for participants

Information for Participants: Perceptions of pine martens and the Pine Marten Recovery Project.

We would like to ask you to participate in research investigating perceptions of a proposed Pine Marten translocation by the Vincent Wildlife Trust.

Through this research, we aim to better understand:

- What people think of pine martens.
- What people think of the Pine Marten Recovery Project
- What benefits people think the project will have.
- What challenges we might face implementing the project.

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary. It will involve a meeting and conversation at a mutually agreed time and location. With your permission, the conversation will be audio recorded. Recordings will not be shared with any individuals outside the research team. If you would prefer not to be recorded, the researcher will take written notes. You can also request that the audio recording be switched off at any time during the conversation.

Only the research team will have access to the research data itself. When publishing results, we will use pseudonyms and respondents' identities will be protected as much as possible in the final project and any associated publications. Representatives of organisations can choose whether or not they also wish their organisation to be anonymised.

You may decide not to answer any of the researcher's questions if you wish. You may also decide to withdraw from this study at any time by advising the researcher at the time of your meeting, or by emailing davidbavin@vwt.org.uk or using the contact detail at the end of this document. If you notify us of your withdrawal, all identifiable data will be destroyed.

We may ask for clarification of issues raised in the meeting at some time after it has taken place, but you will not be obliged in any way to clarify or participate further.

There are no known or anticipated risks to you as a participant in this research.

If you have any questions regarding this project or would like additional information, please ask the researcher before, during, or after your meeting. Contact details for the primary researcher and the supervisory team are provided below.

S2e: Consent form (variation on template used in all studies)

Consent form

Please tick the boxes to confirm your agreement with the corresponding statements:

I have read the letter of invitation / information sheet, and understood the information given about the project and what my participation involves

I know that I am free to withdraw my participation at any time

I know that I can choose not to answer any question

Please delete as appropriate

I agree to an audio recording of my interview YES / NO

Signed (participant) _____ Date _____

Signed (researcher) _____ Date _____